

Public Relations in Collegiate Sports at a Midwestern University

Bachchu Shekh, A K M Zamir Uddin and Adam Beck

Abstract

Public relations strategies demonstrate various narratives to advance their agenda by applying multiple communication tools, disseminating messages from an individual or an organization to the public, and aiming to influence their perception. In sports at a Midwestern university, public relations accomplish and endorse practices to ensure the image of sports, athletes, and teams through various media. Public relations professionals have a significant role in sports public relations at the Midwestern university, building relationships among multiple entities like media, teams, sponsors, advertisers, fans, and other outside organizations. This study included interviews with various communication offices ($N=6$) (e.g., strategic communication, university communication, public relations, athletics department, and radio station) at a large Midwestern University and local areas to learn their experiences and public relations strategies. Results indicate that participants emphasized using social media platforms and print and digital newspapers. Results also found some strategies to encounter crisis in sports on addressing misinformation. Findings suggest that the Midwestern university formed a strong media team and disseminated various roles among individuals to ensure effective campaigns. These results offer insight into how public relations strategies determine and influence sports in a university.

Keywords: Public Relations, Sports, University

Public Relations in Collegiate Sports at a Midwestern University

The use of Public Relations (PR) enables a university to demonstrate its various activities, including academic programs at both undergraduate and graduate levels, cultural events, and sports activities among students and the public. Effective PR strategies enhance a university's brand image, reputation, and overall perception among the public. Graduate schools within the university use innovative PR tactics to help it attract donors that ultimately mobilize the required funds for the graduate school to run smoothly. This helps strengthen the university's name and fame in a competitive educational landscape. The vibrant PR activities of a university also serve as a bridge between alumni and the current students. It also assists a university in strengthening its engagement with the external community. To achieve this, the PR officials are involved in diversified activities, including maintaining a vibrant relationship with reporters from both print and digital media outlets.

Promotional works in graduate school are not a new phenomenon (Wernick, 1991), and marketing is gradually turning into a core part of higher education practices (Foskett, 2010). PR is increasingly emerging as one of the most significant components of a university's promotional strategies (Cronin, 2016). PR principles are now essential aspects of how a graduate school thinks, manages, and engages with the public to explain the value of higher education in society.

From this perspective, the findings of this study will help graduate schools use different PR methods to address the ongoing issues. Along with discussing the regular PR activities of the Midwestern university, this study discussed how a Midwestern university's various PR departments handle several situational crises involving sports and building collaborations and its challenges related to misinformation. Following this section, the literature review is discussed, and then methodological considerations and research questions are

highlighted. The following sections focus on results, discussion, limitations of the study, and future research ideas sequentially.

Literature Review

The literature review of this paper discusses how public relations has developed over the years. It also highlighted several PR strategies that are now popular among corporate entities. This section also discussed how and why educational institutions now emphasize PR as an academic discipline.

Public Relations Concepts and Definitions

The short history of modern public relations proposes many definitions, explanations, metaphors, and approaches to this field. Hutton (1999) observes that public relations pioneer Ivy Lee, considered the father of modern public relations who had a significant role in developing the discipline (Barnum et al., 1999) even feels ambiguity or confusion about a proper explanation about PR. He, however, emphasized honesty, understanding, and compromise to ensure an appropriate adjustment between the interrelations of public and business. He frequently thought of himself as a person who delivered information and performed as a kind of lawyer, representing his clients in the court of public opinion. Similarly, Bernays (1947) found that public relations are an effort to inform, persuade, and make an adjustment with a view to engineering public support for an event, activity, cause, movement, or institution.

During the mid-1970s, Harlow (1977) carried out an analysis on the evaluation of the public relations definition. In the first couple of decades of the last century, the most influential theme in public relationships was building and holding goodwill based on communication. In the 1940s-decade, public relations were defined using several kinds of causes, including as a guide to social conduct, social and political engineering, developer of goodwill, builder of public

opinion, and so on. Between the 1950s and 60s, some other metaphors were included, such as lubricant, pilot, catalyst, and so on. Harlow (1976) synthesized a definition that stemmed from 472 different definitions and input from 65 practitioners. He found the following:

Public relations is a distinctive management function that helps establish and maintain mutual lines of communication, understanding, acceptance, and cooperation between an organization and its public; involves the management of problems or issues; helps management to keep informed on and responsive to public opinion; defines and emphasizes the responsibility of management to serve the public interest; helps management keep abreast of and effectively utilize change, serving as an early warning system to help anticipate trends; and uses research and sound and ethical communication techniques as its principal tools. (P. 36)

This definition successfully linked the relationship between the public and the organization. Hutton (1999) states that the most common definitional components appear to be management, organization, and the public in public relations. Practitioner definitions tend to focus on management, organization, and the public.

Public Relations Strategies

Creativity and efficiency is the central theme of all public relations, marketing communications, and related activities. The public relations teams of organizations follow various strategies to achieve their goals. All types of business organizations- whether big or small, profit or nonprofit, local or global – have a clear objective. Objectives may include making a profit, influencing legislation, or contributing positively to the community. The purpose of every public relations professional is to help their organization so that business objectives can be achieved. So, a clear objective helps a public relations team to set its primary

strategy (Anderson et al., 2009). The initial strategy of a public relations team is to focus on the objectives.

Taking corporate social responsibility (CSR) program is another important strategy for a public relations team. CSR is a tool that helps a company strengthen its position in the market (Handelman & Stephen, 1999) by displaying its positive and ethical stance to the local people (Sen & Bhattacharya, 2001). A responsible and sustainable company usually emphasizes including ethical standards in its strategy and uses those standards thoughtfully. A similar situation exists in PR since it is a set of actions aimed at getting the desired response from target groups and building and maintaining a relationship with them.

Event marketing is another important strategic approach that helps to shine a brand or organization through the planning and execution of events in a successful manner (Tafesse, 2016). It is a strong marketing tool that allows corporate organizations to create meaningful connections with their target audience, produce brand awareness, and achieve specific marketing objectives. Brand marketing is now considered a major PR tool to make visible the brand of a product or service among customers.

The crisis response strategy is another vital program for a public relations team. When a crisis attacks a company, public relations professionals are called on as communication experts to protect the brand image or reputation. Experts can also play a significant role in repairing a company's reputation that a crisis has lost. These brand and image repair strategies depend on the effective use of language, persuasive message strategies, and symbolic actions (Benoit, 2008). Similarly, Coombs and Holladay (2020) observe that following a crisis, an appropriate response strategy also helps the organization reduce the level of damage during times of crisis. Some other public relations strategies, such as preparing advertising and message development (Hwang et

al., 2003) and Tenderich (2019), are also followed by public relations teams with the utmost importance.

Public Relations in Sports

For many years, sports and public relations were uniquely defined as a separate occupational and academic specialism (Serbanica & Constantinescu, 2016). However, a broadly accepted definition is that sports public relations is a managerial communication-based function designed to identify a sports organization's key public segments, evaluate its relationships with those segments, and foster desirable relationships between the sports organization and those segments (Stoldt et al., 2006). Academic research exploring sports public relations topics is relatively limited but appears to be increasing as scholars in public relations and related disciplines have published various related studies in academic journals (Issacson, 2010). In intercollegiate athletics contexts, PR research has primarily focused on the personnel who demonstrate/occupy those PR roles and the characteristics of those individuals. However, few studies focus on tying those personnel directly to roles, except for some management vs. technician distinctions in job duties and perceptions (Ruihley et.al., 2016). Schools generate considerable revenue from sports, allowing them to increase their statuses as institutions and continue to expand as communities.

A core component in ensuring this monetary support is the development of external relations, such as building relationships with various publics. These publics range anywhere from students to prospective students, alumni, academic communities, and sports fans, each playing a key role in its respective area of support (McMillian, 2014). Although there is the potential for different sports crises on a university campus, a big crisis affecting collegiate sports has created a seismic shift in the collegiate landscape (Peterson & Judge, 2021). One is the Name, Image, and

Likeness (NIL) crisis. The NIL is a set of policies that create avenues for student-athletes to benefit financially from their NIL through deals and sponsorships. Students can profit from anything that is not a direct reward, compensation-wise, for their athletic performance. These sponsorships allow athletes to develop their brand and create a career outside their athletic performance (Henderson, 2023). How has this developed into a crisis that continues to cause chaos on college campuses?

Sports Crisis

One area in which the National Collegiate Athletic Association (NCAA) establishes rules pertains to the amateur status of student-athletes. The NCAA's principle of amateurism, as drafted and approved by its membership, states that "student-athletes shall be amateurs in an intercollegiate sport, and their participation shall be motivated by education and by the physical, mental and social benefits to be derived." (Edelman, 2013). Most NCAA members have fully abided by the NCAA's principle of amateurism, even though it has meant that college athletic directors and coaches earn millions of dollars while student-athletes continue to live below the poverty line. The NCAA amateurism bylaws have served as an impediment as violations could result in penalties levied against the institution. There has been a long-standing debate regarding whether student-athletes should receive compensation in exchange for their participation in college sports. NCAA member institutions have harbored other concerns; they believe that compensating college players could result in an inequitable recruiting process, as it could open the door to impropriety, such as a pay-for-play model (King, 2024). In 2019, California passed Senate Bill 206, known as the "Fair Pay to Play Act," allowing college athletes to earn compensation for their Name, Image, and Likeness (NIL) and obtain professional representation

that was initially to become effective in 2023 (Tenjido, 2021). This California legislation spurred 26 other states to pass similar NIL laws (Dosh, 2021).

In 2019, several current and former college athletes sued the NCAA in a case called *NCAA v. Alston*. In this case, the athletes sought to challenge the NCAA's rules limiting the compensation that student-athletes could receive, arguing that they were in violation of federal antitrust law. At the time, student-athlete compensation was limited to education-related benefits. Applying the "rule of reason" analysis, in 2021, the Supreme Court agreed with the lower courts and found that the NCAA's rules limiting player compensation were unreasonable because they substantially suppressed and destroyed the competition, thus violating the Sherman Act. The Supreme Court ruled that the association could not bar member schools from offering certain education-related benefits to student-athletes (Claybourn, 2024). This case has been characterized as one of U.S. history's most important sports law decisions (Taylor, 2022).

In the absence of federal legislation, interim rules for states regarding NIL were established almost immediately. These actions included allowing athletes to use professional service providers for their NIL activities but required athletes to report their activities as the schools must determine the consistency of these NIL activities with state law (Peterson & Judge, 2021). Moody (2023), wrote that following the introduction of NIL rights, collectives began to emerge and quickly spread. Essentially, these collectives are non-profits that are affiliated with but operate independently from a particular school and its athletic department. They raise funds to create opportunities for student-athletes to leverage their NIL in exchange for compensation. Since their inception, these collectives have become controversial as questions have arisen about their legality and potential role in recruiting (Claybourn, 2023). This has established a need for congressional legislation to figure it out.

Sports and the Importance of Public Relations

Public relations are often considered communication and promotional tools. In the world of sports, public relations also have a significant role to play. Isaacson (2010) states that sports public relations include media relations, new media, print media, design and web management, community relations, various promotional activities, event management, integrated relations, and sports marketing. In sports organizations, the role of public relations is unsurmountable, considering its strategies and use as a widely recognized marketing tool.

In sports, public relations appear to be an actual communication opportunity designed to construct an overview of sympathy and cooperation from the public (Petrovici & Dobrescu, 2013). It explores a prolific communication tool that influences athletes' branding and team management and ensures fan engagement. According to Kunczik (2002), at present, public relations represent a sophisticated way of fostering an organization and assisting it in promoting its products and services, making and maintaining sustainable and reliable relationships that enhance trust in the target audiences of different groups of people.

On a broader scale, public relations strategies are often utilized in sports marketing, event management, and crisis communication within the sports industries and fields. From a marketing point of view, every sporting event and tournament attracts more public interest; therefore, arranging such events has a great potential to make a profit by employing marketing activities (Tomic, 2007). Any sports event usually connects various marketing resources to any sporting society, club, franchise, competition organizer, sports person, and coach, while marketing and public relations play a crucial role.

It is well known that crisis communication can sometimes severely hamper a company's efforts and marketing policy, which are invaluable and tangible assets for their brand reputation

(Dawar & Pillutla, 2000). However, the strategic role of public relations is immense, while sports marketers consider PR practices ensuring media monitoring to assess the crisis and the audiences' emotional feedback to it (LaGree et al., 2019). Considering these issues can make a strong crisis management platform to uphold the reputation and fame of the sports organization. Considering the context of sports, relationships are seen as a practical element of public relations, while Mullin et al. (2007) defined public relations in sports as the following:

An interactive marketing communications strategy seeks to create a variety of media designed to convey organizational philosophies, goals, and objectives to an identified group of the public to establish a relationship built on comprehension, interest, and support (p. 385).

It underscores the strategic importance of marketing communications in creating relationship-building. This relationship can be achieved by conveying the organization's values and goals through different media and the public to establish a strong connection.

Public Education

The ongoing demand for public relations in education focuses on how academic institutions implement public relations strategies to attain their fame and reputation, targeting the target groups and attracting students. According to Kiesenbauer and Zerfass (2015), public relations education greatly emphasizes providing students with various tools and necessary skills to succeed in the industry, particularly in emerging fields. The study of public relations seeks professional affiliation, viewing the concept of public relations as a means of attaining this (L'Etang & Pieczka, 2006). According to Sriramesh (2003), PR students must be adequately equipped with diverse resources to become effective multicultural professionals and incorporate various insights and viewpoints into the PR educational curriculum. Similarly, the role of public

relations activities in collegiate sports is vital. It helps any athletic department assess its vision, mission, concerned staff, and organizers in many ways and, in many cases, which is much needed (Ruihley et al., 2016).

Through public relations activities and campaigns, educational institutions can build a strong communication strategy and adopt programs that promote a promotional attitude and overview to the target group. By applying PR strategies in sports, various organizations can benefit by raising public awareness of their products, services, and brands, which will help them enjoy their advantages and image (Beech & Chadwick, 2007). In the age of digital communication, using social media in PR for collegiate sports has become a common phenomenon. In contrast to larger institutions, smaller universities gain huge media exposure through social media campaigns by arranging successful athletic events (Lee et al., 2008). This is why social media creates various opportunities for the teams seeking an online presence, as Facebook and Twitter play significant roles along with the media outlets (Moore, 2011). Kowalski (2011) opined that in a society focused on innovation, public schools face numerous competitions from other academic institutions, offering guardians and targeted students various educational events and programs. Public relations offers the best option for marketing and promoting services and has become more effective in public relations education.

Considering the holistic approach and public relations strategies, this study explores deeper insights into PR strategies in collegiate sports, addressing the communication, advertising, and marketing policies used by various forms of media. PR is a unique concept that creates various communication channels, realizing the nature of relationships and cooperation among organizations and the public. As a result, individuals might experience additional observation and exposure to define and implement PR strategies in sports during collegiate

events at a Midwestern university. Given the issue into consideration, the following research questions are to be proposed to discover the attempts of this study:

RQ1: What PR strategies are implemented in Midwestern university?

RQ2: How PR strategies help to overcome challenges during collegiate sports competition?

Recruitment

Participants were recruited through email correspondence. Each participant had been involved in various communication offices (e.g., strategic communication, university communication, public relations, athletics department, and radio station) at a large, midwestern university and local areas. Following IRB approval, the research team communicated individually with all participants to set up an interview date. Before participating in an interview, each participant agreed and completed the approved consent form. All the interviews were conducted over the Zoom online meeting platform.

Participants

A total of six individuals ($N=6$) participated in the research. Each of them was involved in public relations and sports for several years. The breakdown of the research demographic included five men ($n=5$) and one woman ($n=1$) between the ages of 32 and 61 ($M=51.66$). All the participants were identified as Caucasian (100%). All reside in a large midwestern city in the U.S. and adjacent areas. Five individuals have a master's degree (83.3%), and one has a bachelor's degree (16.6%).

Data Collection

Data was collected through semi-structured, in-depth online interviews. Following informed written consent, the interviewers asked questions. Initially, some general and

demographic questions helped to form a rapport with the interviewees (e.g., How do you define public relations?). Next, questions delved into their roles and experiences with public relations and communication (e.g., How many years of involvement with public relations do you have?). Finally, some other questions like marketing, public relations, and sports were also asked (e.g., It could be argued that marketing and public relations go together, especially when it comes to sports. Can you tell us what you think about this?), while questions about challenges and adaptability were also discussed (e.g., What are some public relations challenges you are currently facing?).

Questions were framed and designed to be open-ended, and participants were encouraged to discuss their experiences and thoughts in public relations, crisis communication, sports communication, and strategic communication. The interviews ranged from 21 to 72 minutes ($M=49.49$). The interviews were transcribed, producing 92 pages of double-spaced data. The interviews were thoroughly checked to confirm accuracy and anonymity.

Data Analysis

To explore the public relations strategies followed in a midwestern university while overcoming prospective challenges during collegiate sports, the dataset was analyzed using thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006). First, two interview transcripts were open-coded line-by-line. During the first step, each line of data was given a code that rightly represented and embodied the idea and action in that line of data (Glaser & Strauss, 1967; Strauss & Corbin, 1998). Following the constant comparative method (Charmaz, 2006; Corbin & Strauss, 2008), reoccurring codes were continuously refined as new data was collected and coded. Next, reoccurring codes were included in a codebook. Using focused coding, the codebook was then applied to the remaining dataset by identifying participants' experiences that fit into each code.

Finally, axial coding was used to determine the connections among those themes (Charmaz, 2006). Data collection stopped once data saturation (i.e., when no new codes, themes or details emerged from the data) was approached before the sixth interview. Each participant was given a pseudonym to ensure confidentiality.

Throughout the data collection and analysis, vigilant and careful consideration were given to ensure rigor and credibility. Based on Tracy's (2010) eight "big tent" criteria for securing high-quality qualitative research, researchers' followed various strategies to establish trustworthiness in the findings. In this stage, first, we engaged in memo writing throughout data collection and analysis to record early impressions of the data and to establish a record of decisions surrounding data analysis. Second, we met together with our coding process to explore the data and label the themes, while focusing on rich description of each category using participants' words, which provided evidence and findings for ensuring credibility of our research. Finally, we focused on reflexivity by seeking to understand us to ensure that the data were rather than our own experiences and beliefs (Charmaz, 2006).

Results

This study found eight separate themes to describe how PR is used successfully at a Midwestern university. The university uses several strategies to make its PR events successful. Along with print and digital newspapers, the PR officials of the midwestern university are focusing on social media sites to carry out their PR activities. They also highlighted their difficulties in doing PR within collegiate sports. They also stated the activities that they use to figure out various issues. Each of the eight themes are described in the following sections.

Social Media Platforms: An Effective Tool for PR Campaign

Social media sites play a vital role in communicating with both internal and external communities of the university. The concerned officials of the public relations department consider social media platforms as a great tool to campaign their agenda successfully. One of the officials of the PR department said that the department has a social media manager, who constantly monitors social media sites. The office also has a group of graduate assistants to help keep the public relations staff up-to-date on contemporary social trends. Although it is difficult to gauge the success of the PR campaign, social media monitoring is also helping to provide an idea about the effectiveness of the events. According to the official, “We keep a tally of those, like, how many we have monthly, you know, how many we have for each college at the University? How many are positive, how many are negative ... They do something similar on the social media sites, keeping track of, you know, things like reach, and likes and follows and all that jazz.” This means the process is providing a hint about the success of their PR activities as well.

Another official also echoed the same sentiment about social media:

“We can see how many people are looking at our website, and how many people are responding to our social media posts, and we know that it is up over the last four years. For example, we track our Twitter handle and how many people are followers of Missouri State men’s basketball or women’s basketball, that is a great place to start.”

He said that using social media platforms – Twitter, Facebook, and Instagram – to promote the games by exchanging information is a very effective tactic. Another official said, “We educate not only our athletes, but also all faculty and staff, and every other student. And so even though we don't monitor each individual, we have social media guidelines in place. The guidelines give instructions on what you can and what you can't post if you

are representing an organization and managing your page. We monitor the posts when the individuals upload them to make sure they are following compliance.”

Each athletic program has its own individual social media accounts. He said, “We do offer suggestions, and we have the community requesting to engage in open conversation, in particular with our team members. We have over 400 athletes, and probably over 100 staff members that are coaches, or athletic trainers, or, you know, academic, whoever it might be. It is a reminder for our coaches, and our athletes, that they are public figures in the community. The public follows their accounts. Becoming good role models is important to represent the employer efficiently.”

Having a viable social media presence is vital but surrounding yourself with people that are highly skilled in that aspect is crucial.

Print and Digital Newspapers Still Getting Priority

The midwestern university also uses both print and electronic media to carry out its PR campaign in a successful manner. An employee of the university’s PR department said that he tried to follow closely both print and digital newspapers regularly, which are available in the town. The content published by the newspapers shapes the public perception to a large degree. So, the university emphasizes publishing content of public relations in the newspapers. On the other hand, the majority of individuals are still depending on newspapers to get updates on university events, highlighting the significance of newspaper content in bringing these matters to the forefront of public attention, according to the official.

Mentioning a journalist during his initial job career, he said,

“Things like writing press releases and feature stories is the favorite for me as I was a journalist. One of my jobs is to find nuggets of information around the university

and pitch them to different news outlets, but it requires a lot of research into not just the outlet itself, but the reporters and what they might find interesting or what they might pick up on and then having the correct timing.”

Another official thinks that a PR official should maintain a vibrant relationship with newspaper reporters. Sometimes, they want to know about some unusual event that happened on the campus, and they also ask the PR officials to this end. Against the backdrop, the PR officials suggest the reporters contact with the concerned university employee or the faculty who may provide information to the reporters. This is why the PR officials should maintain good relationships with both internal and external communities of the university to make PR events effective.

Maintaining Vibrant Relationships with Alumni

The PR department plays a significant role in raising funds from individuals for the university. A senior official of the PR department said that building and maintaining a vibrant relationship with alumni helps manage the targeted funds. For example, they had set a target of mobilizing funds amounting to \$250 million for a fundraising campaign. He said,

“In a campaign, you have a quiet phase where you do not really announce it publicly.

You need to raise about 60 percent of the goal before you go to the public. And we went public in 2019, And then we concluded the campaign with big successful event in the fall of 2022. It was to raise \$250 million, which we got to \$274 million.”

The official thinks that maintaining relationships with each type of audience is important as many donors are not alumni, and everybody can be a donor to Missouri State. He also suggests the need to educate the internal audiences of the university concerning the future event. The employee said, “We have to educate students about what we do, because this is a lifelong

organization. In other words, you are a student for four years, but who you are really what you do with us, for the rest of your life matters. And we want that relationship to be lifelong.”

Creating A Professional Network

The field of PR is ever-changing, so a sound professional network helps understand the change in keeping with time. A senior official of the PR department of the university said that they always try to connect a vibrant relationship with several kinds of individual professionals and their organizations to make their campaigns are effective. He said,

“We are not alone in that, you know, everybody wants to be in good standing with this university because of their standing in the community with all the employees and you know, just how big it is in the state of Missouri. I am involved in several different civic clubs and organizations, so there is a lot of potential to have networking opportunities, and connections with other businesses or organizations where I’m learning constantly. I always look at it as I need to always be learning because the public relations field is ever-changing.”

Another official said that there is a campus PR Association for students. This is a good way to get involved from the onset.

Challenges of Public Relations and its Strategic Roles Addressing the Crisis

Crises are a reality in today’s world, and they must be anticipated. In athletics, a crisis is defined as any event which threatens personal safety or jeopardizes the short or long-term image, reputation or financial stability of an athletic department or institution. It is important to realize that within a plan, there will be a variety of different things that affect it. This study found two sub-themes that described how the university handle challenges and crisis to communicate with internal and external communities: addressing misinformation and addressing PR crises in spots

Addressing Misinformation

The university sometimes encounters misinformation related to a crisis. However, it does not happen very often. When it does, the PR officials of the university treat the issue with utmost importance to tackle the misinformation by way of taking several kinds of measures. One of the participants said, “There's not a ton of misinformation. Honestly, when it comes to the university, because we're a public university, we're very open to people. Another interviewee said, “We typically sit down with the parties and stress the importance of not releasing that information. You need to have that conversation, when it happens, because we have to involve the football coaching staff, the athletic director, other people, and so we have to use that as a learning experience to say in the next project, do not do this because it looks bad”.

Addressing Public Relations Crisis in Sports

Some of the participants said that they encountered difficulties in carrying out PR in collegiate sports. There are several crises they are facing including decreasing attendance at sports events. However, the PR department in athletics has taken several initiatives to increase attendance in various sports events. Out of all the questions, the one about declining attendance and the one about the Name, Image and Likeness (NIL) phenomenon, seemed to really trigger participants especially those that are close to the issues. A participant said that the dwindling attendance at sporting events especially basketball is a major challenge. There are reasons for this lack of attendance. One reason is that can be attributed to the siloing of groups. One participant said

“We have a university communications department that's housed in athletics, and they do all the news releases, spit out the information, keep the stats of games, and they are also the sports information people. We also have an outside third party called Learfield. They

sell stuff like signage in the arena, game sponsorships, radio, tv ads, in game promotions, ticket promotion and basically, they are marketing to a degree. Because each of those are all important, they have to work together, and I don't think that it is happening here. They are not university employees; they are their own company. However, both groups have to work together more to have the end product of having more people buy tickets, more people, organizations wanting to be in the arena, with signage, and then we have to get that information out to season ticket holders and others about promotions and the in-game experience, so it's not a one person does at all type of thing”.

The participants were really fired up about the NIL and the problems with it. One participant said “It has created a ‘wild wild west show’ among collegiate sports because the rules change constantly. There are major problems with this. One of things is the lack of consistency. The problem is that the rules change on this from the NCAA almost every day, and states can regulate their own.” He said that there is now a state law in Missouri where you can have institutions that internally raise money for NIL and hand it out and other states where you can't. He said, “It's a mess. On the one hand, we need to raise more money for name image and likeness for student athletes and by Missouri law, you can do it internally. However, the NCAA law says no, you must have these outside groups raise money for you, and then they distribute the money to the student athletes. It's going to be a bigger mess in the future until we have a universal rule.” He said that there is some speculation that Congress will probably have some sort of legislation on this. However, the result will be that student athletes will be getting paid. “We are navigating this now trying to figure out what to do”.

Building Collaboration with External Entities

There is an immense impact of maintaining external collaboration as it makes PR campaigns successful. External partnerships of the university can exist in a variety of ways. One participant who is the general manager of a local sports radio station explained the external relationship saying that the station is the “flagship station for the university in the major sports like football, men's and women's basketball. Part of this partnership also involves having every bit of news or sports that the university releases on both of our websites. One of those websites is our News Talk website and one is our all sports website.”

One of the keys to good collaborations is through partnerships. One participant said “When it comes to outside the university partnerships, that usually is good PR. When we partner with other organizations like the Alliance for Health Care Education that the university is doing with a local school district, the community college and an area hospital, that's a big one and that's good PR for the university. Sometimes we do things with our local school district which is a big one. If some of our students are doing something really cool with one of their students, you know, we will co-post on social media stories like that. So, I think that community collaboration is usually good for the university”. This was echoed by another participant who said, “having good collaboration is key whether it's with the city, or when we went through that with the COVID crisis a couple of years ago, where we were in constant collaboration with the city and the county and the state health board, on whether we could have a game whether our players could travel”.

Another way external partnerships exists is talking to colleagues in the field outside the university through going to conferences or talking to former employers. One participant said “I think about the times when I talked to people about how I should handle some things, there's people that I've worked with in the past, and I asked them. It could also either be people that are

sports information directors, which are the PR persons for the athletic department, or it could be people outside of athletics like an ad agency.

Staying Involved with Changes in the Field

The university's various PR staff always try to learn and adapt from the changes in the field as it is deemed one of the vital components to be successful. One participant said

“For me, it's being open minded and researching the newest, the latest, greatest, what's working for others. So right now, I spend a large amount of my time in the evenings reading various journals, and following the American Marketing Association on-line and what are they doing. I'm also a member of the National Council for Public Relations Specialists (NCMPR). They're all the time offering advice. They also have online training sessions available, that are that are taught by other industry experts, so people who have gone through situations, that that might be helpful for other institutions”. Considering the changes nature of this profession, always getting involved in various organizations helps PR professionals keep updated.

Another challenge is simply embracing the moment. One participant said

“A lot of my communications background probably came from crisis communication. I have had extensive training in crisis communication and so that's probably the biggest part of what my trainings are in. I don't have a journalism background so I can write news releases, but I'm not a professional. I don't claim to be a professional writing the greatest news article or anything like that. In my current role, I never hope that a crisis is going to come up, but you know, a crisis can be defined in some people's eyes as man that's a small thing but to others no that's a pretty big crisis. So, I think it's shaped my communication being able to connect with people more extensively. I think it's certainly

made me more outgoing than I used to be. I think because it's forced me outside my element”.

Finally, another participant also said “I’m involved in several civic organizations, because you should be involved in your community. This provides networking opportunities, connections with other businesses or organizations, and learning constantly”. So, it proves whatever background you are, you must have some experiences or have that level of interest to cope up with the changes of the field and learning new things to constantly to overcome any obstacles.

Discussion

Participants utilized a common theme of different challenges to describe staying involved with the various changes in the public relations field. Additionally, they identified two challenges to staying involved with changes in the field. One of those was the importance of staying up to date on training required. In the academic context, to keep up to date, researchers use various information resources, many of which have become available online through search engines and web alerts. Many scientific and technical publications, and more recently books, can be relatively easily accessed online (Martin & Quan-Haase, 2013). The participants did this via different ways. One way is to visit on-line business information sites and use social media sites like LinkedIn, staying with their state and national entities and attending seminars on public relations where they will talk about the newest innovations in public relations. One participant spoke of being at a small two-year university and he stays up to date by reading stuff on-line in the evenings and being a part of public relations organizations. In small organizations, all the duties related to employee relations and communication may be vested in one public relations or

human resources employee. No matter who is assigned the duties, the responsibility is as communicator, interpreter, and persuader for the employer (Center, 2014).

Another challenge participants faced was embracing the moment in public relations. For some of the participants, they do what Ledingham and Bruning (2000) describe when they argue that Grunig's (1992) concept of public relations as "building relationships with publics that enhance the ability of the organization to meet its mission" was instrumental in shifting the emphasis in public relations from managing publics and public opinion to a new emphasis on building, nurturing, and maintaining relationships. The participants hope they never have a crisis come up but are ready should one happen

Maintaining Vibrant Relationships with Alumni

Relationships with alumni are critical to the success of the university. Some of the participants spoke about the need for this as relationships with alumni help provide funding for various things at the university and to secure the future of the university. This is evidenced by the fact that colleges and universities are now being ranked, among other criteria, on this kind of alumni support as evidenced by the US News and World Report's Guide to the Best Colleges. As a result, many colleges are propelled to increase alumni support lest lack of support detract from their institution's ranking (Levine, 2008). Alumni are unique stakeholders for an institution, because the more their institutions grow in stature, the better it is for the alumni (Cuthbert, 2002). Universities must provide a strong foundation for future alumni to do well in life, including a good education from a dedicated faculty and a healthy value system of academic honesty, hard work, and professionalism. The alumni's support and voluntary contributions to their universities play a critical role in the maintenance and expansion of these universities (Kumar, 2008). This was talked about by a participant and was seen in a recent campaign, where

the goal was very high and having a Hollywood A-Lister who was an alum as a campaign chair and yet at least one participant also mentioned that it's also hard to create these relationships if they are an athlete with the transfer portal in place. That participant mentioned that it used to be that fans would get to know a player over four years and establish a bond, but now if you are fan, you barely even get to know the player.

Building Collaborations with External Entities

Industry-university collaborations have been around for a long-time there has been a growing trend in colleges and universities to better connect campuses with their communities (Wodicka et al., 2012). The participants had very interesting collaborations with external entities and vice versa. These collaborations can be as simple as being the flagship radio station of the university sports but not letting that get in the way of being very professional in their dealings with the university to more elaborate ones like the partnership with organizations like the Alliance for Health Care Education that the university is doing with a local school district, the community college and an area hospital. These collaborations weren't forced but were born out of necessity but make for good public relations for the university. Collaborations are more than just working on a project together but some of the participants even talked about how it can be seeing colleagues in the field outside the university through going to a conference. The importance of this was something that English poet John Donne (1624) was hinting at when he wrote, "No man is an island entire of itself; every man is a piece of the continent, a part of the main."

Creating Professional Network

The concept of Public Relations is becoming increasingly important in college athletics as the frequency and severity of controversy, legal issues, and crises heighten (Ruihley et al.,

2016). To help combat this, participants stressed the importance of having a vibrant relationship with several kinds of individual professionals and their organizations. The process of developing and maintaining relationships with strategic publics is a crucial component of strategic management, issues management, and crisis management (Hon & Grunig, 1999). A participant talked about this when he talked about the moment that his campus decided to have a rodeo team and how it has been a catalyst in elevating our academic program on the agriculture side. He also talked how his campus was gifted a farm recently so they could house horses and cattle and have a place for a practice arena and livestock. So that opened the door for new academic programs like a veterinary tech program, and a veterinary assistant program. We are using that rodeo program to leverage what we're doing on the academic side with that vet tech and vet assistant program. It's certainly the athletic side that has helped us market this new ag program, because we are seeing students who are coming in now that wouldn't have otherwise. As part of this professional network, participants also mentioned how marketing and public relations go together hand in hand but they need to be coordinated. because you have more emphasis on marketing than you do PR.

Theoretical and Practical Implications

Findings of this research indicate that the field of PR is dynamic which requires professionally updated, skilled and experienced staff. Participants must be open to have continuous learning and developing skills to adapt in PR professions and practices. Findings of the present study suggest that building relationships in PR for the long-term plays a crucial role to the success of the midwestern university. Participants who are designated to maintain outside collaborations emphasized having flagship relationships and partnership with organizations, even if it comes with outside academia. This PR strategy should actively enhance the university's

visibility and impact on the target audiences during the sporting events. According to Grunig (2000), the fundamental principle of public relations should have emphasis on the collaboration, relating with the ideas of societal corporatism, collectivism, and communal relationships. Findings also suggest that there should always be an integration of a marketing policy and PR strategies to constantly provide consistent and impactful messaging.

Additionally, these findings add to current research on employing a social media manager along with distinct groups to monitor the success of PR activities through various social media platforms. Valentini and Kruckeberg (2012) argue that “social media must be at the heart of public relations activities because social media can enhance organization relationships by increasing and improving community relations (p. 11).” For participants, maintaining relationships with print and online media has a great significant in public relations practices, cooperating with journalist to get news coverage of sports events. Addressing misinformation, the PR team at the midwestern university follows a two-step strategy. First, they establish direct communication with channels and individuals to root out on how the misinformation got spread, while considering collaborative efforts with athletes and concerned coaching staff to encounter the misinformation together. Second, once they find the misinformation, the PR team at the midwestern university then analyzes the situation and follows a strategy collaborating with both external and internal entities to disseminate the correct information through various media and channels.

Scholars have acknowledged organizations usually provide information through various technologies to make crisis responses to the misinformation. Currently, various organizations are considering and leveraging social media and different communication technologies to innovate and adapt their crisis responses (Siau & Han, 2020, Wade & Shan, 2020, Yang et al., 2020).

Through various PR strategies, participants can effectively demonstrate proactive PR strategies in managing a crisis at Midwestern university. Findings also suggest that promotional initiatives can help increase attendance at sporting events. The midwestern PR officials implement various promotional initiatives to boost up the attendance at sporting events by utilizing game sponsorships and television advertisements, while offering less-priced tickets to secure more spectators and audiences. Additionally, findings suggest that using metrics such as likes, share and audiences' engagement on various social media campaigns can be an effective way to evaluate PR activities. As such, PR officials follow such a meter to track media coverage and audience feedback for conventional PR activities.

Limitations and Future Considerations

A limitation of a study design or instrument is the systematic bias that the researcher did not or could not control and which could inappropriately affect the results (Price & Murnan, 2004). One of the limitations of the study is the lack of diversity in the pool of data that was collected. Five of the participants in the study identified as white male while one identified as a white female. Further study of this topic could be beneficial to gauge opinions and experiences from a wider range of participants that were based on race or ethnicity to create more a balanced approach. Another limitation is that we focused on selecting participants that could speak to our research protocol questions. The participants from the study were predominately from the midwestern university campus that we were studying as well as its sister campus and the other participant was from a local sports radio station in town. Another limitation is that two of the questions seemed to really overwhelm the rest of the questions in terms of the fact that information regarding them is so current and on-going that participants really were very willing to open up about these. These limitations have caused constraints in the research outcomes.

While this study contributes valuable insights into the area of public relations in collegiate sports, several areas warrant further exploration. One avenue for future research is include a more diversified group to gauge opinions and experiences from a balanced perspective. While this study focused on a particular midwestern university, the research protocol did not lend itself to have students be a part and so a study on students and the impact(s) that various PR departments have would be beneficial.

Another avenue for research is to do a study on the mental health of a student athlete and the impact that the NIL has on student-athletes at the midwestern university. Researchers can gain insights into the underlying challenges that student-athletes face from a mental health point of view. Another avenue of research could be a study on the changing world of public relations when it comes to hybrid work and remote work and how those changes could potentially impact the public relations at the university. Another avenue of research could be on the impact of the lack of marketing for all the collegiate sports teams at the midwestern university. This study could be of benefit to the university in how they market the teams especially in light of the ones that are not money-makers for the university as well as the new ones they recently added like tumbling and gymnastics and even our sister campus has a e-sports team. In conclusion, this study represents a need not only for departments in the university to work together but also for future research endeavors aimed at the changing world of public relations.

References

- Anderson, F. W., Hadley, L., Rockland, D., & Weiner, M. (2009). Guidelines for setting measurable public relations objectives: An update. *Institute for Public Relations*.
- Barnum, T., AGENCY, P., Bernays, E., Page, A., Burson, H., & Kendrix, M. (1999). The history of public relations. *Academia. Edu*.
- Beech, J. G., & Chadwick, S. (Eds.). (2007). *The marketing of sport*. Pearson Education.
- Benoit, W. L. (2008). Image restoration theory. *The International Encyclopedia of Communication*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781405186407.wbieci009.pub2>
- Bernays, E. L. (1947). The engineering of consent. *The Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 250(1), 113-120.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/000271624725000116>
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative research in psychology*, 3(2), 77-101.
- Center, A. H. (2014). *Public relations practices: Managerial case studies and Problems*. Pearson.
- Charmaz, K. (2006). *Constructing grounded theory: A practical guide through qualitative analysis*. Sage publications
- Claybourn C. (2024). Name, Image, Likeness: What college athletes should know about NCAA rules. US News & World Report.
- Coombs, W. T., Holladay, S. J., & White, K. L. (2020). Situational crisis communication theory (SCCT) and application in dealing with complex, challenging, and recurring crises. In *Advancing crisis communication effectiveness* (pp. 165-180). Routledge.

- Corbin, J., & Strauss, A. (2014). *Basics of qualitative research: Techniques and procedures for developing grounded theory*. Sage publications
- Cronin, A. M. (2016). Reputational capital in ‘the PR University’: public relations and market rationalities. *Journal of Cultural Economy*, 9(4), 396-409.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/17530350.2016.1179663>
- Cuthbert, R. (2002). The impact of national developments on institutional practice in S. Ketteridge, S. Marshall and H. Fry (eds.), *The influential academic: A handbook for enhanced academic practice*, London, Kogan, pp. 32- 48.
- Dosh, K. (2021). Tracker: Name, image and likeness legislation by state. *Business of College Sports*. <https://businessofcollegesports.com/tracker-name-image-and-likeness-legislation-by-state/>
- Damásio, M. J., Dias, P., & Andrade, J. G. (2012). The PR Pyramid: Social media and the new role of Public Relations in organizations. *Revista internacional de relaciones públicas*, 2(4), 11-30.
- Dawar, N., & Pillutla, M. M. (2000). Impact of product-harm crises on brand equity: The moderating role of consumer expectations. *Journal of marketing research*, 37(2), 215-226.
- Donne, J. (n.d.). Meditation XVII. The Literature Network. Retrieved from <http://www.onlineliterature.com/donne/409/> (Original work published in 1624).
- Edelman, M. (2013). A Short Treatise on Amateurism and Antitrust Law: Why the NCAA's No-Pay Rules Violate Section 1 of the Sherman Act, 64 Case W. Rsrv. L. Rev. 61 (2013)

- Foskett, N. (2010). Markets, government, funding and the marketisation of UK higher education. In *The marketisation of higher education and the student as consumer* (pp. 39-52). Routledge.
- Glaser, B. G., & Strauss, A. L. (1967). *The discovery of grounded theory: Strategies for qualitative research*. Chicago: Aldine Publishing Company.
- Grunig, J. E. (1992). Excellence in public relations and communication management. Hillsdale, NJ: Erlbaum.
- Grunig, J. E. (2000). Collectivism, collaboration, and societal corporatism as core professional values in public relations. *Journal of public relations research*, 12(1), 23-48.
- Handelman, J. M., & Stephen, J. A. (1999). The role of marketing actions with a social dimension: Appeals to the intuitional environment. *Journal of Marketing*, 63(3), 33-48.
- Harlow, R. F. (1976). Building a public relations definition. *Public relations review*, 2(4), 34-42. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0363-8111\(76\)80022-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0363-8111(76)80022-7)
- Harlow, R. F. (1977). Public relations definitions through the years. *Public Relations Review*, 3, 1, 49-63, Spr 77.
- Havard, Cody T. and Eddy, Terry (2013) "Qualitative Assessment of Rivalry and Conference Realignment in Intercollegiate Athletics," *Journal of Issues in Intercollegiate Athletics*, 6(15).
- Hon, L & Grunig, J. (1999). Guidelines for measuring relationships in public relations. Institute for Public Relations
- Hutton, J. G. (1999). The definition, dimensions, and domain of public relations. *Public relations review*, 25(2), 199-214. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0363-8111\(99\)80162-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0363-8111(99)80162-3)

- Hwang, J. S., McMillan, S. J., & Lee, G. (2003). Corporate web sites as advertising: An analysis of function, audience, and message strategy. *Journal of Interactive Advertising*, 3(2), 10-23. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15252019.2003.10722070>
- Issacson, T. (2010). Sport Public Relations. In R. Heath (Ed.), *The SAGE Handbook of Public Relations*. (p. 599-609) SAGE Publications.
- King, A. (2024). Name, Image, and Likeness in US College Athletics: One Year Later. *The National Law Review*, 14(78). <https://www.natlawreview.com/article/name-image-and-likeness-us-college-athletics-one-year-later>
- Kowalski, T. J. (2011). Public relations in schools.
- Kumar, K. (2008). Partners in education. *Economic and Political Weekly* 43 (3), 8-11.
- Kunczik, M. (2010). *Public Relations: Konzepte und Theorien*. utb GmbH.
- LaGree, D., Wilbur, D., & Cameron, G. T. (2019). A strategic approach to sports crisis management: Assessing the NFL concussion crisis from marketing and public relations perspectives. *International Journal of Sports Marketing and Sponsorship*, 20(3), 407-429.
- Ledingham, J., & Bruning, S. (2000). (Eds.), *Public relations as relationship management: A relational approach to the study and practice of public relations*. Hillsdale, NJ: Erlbaum.
- Lee, J. W., Miloch, K. S., Kraft, P., & Tatum, L. (2008). Building the brand: a case study of Troy University. *Sport Marketing Quarterly*, 17(3).
- Lee, L. W., Yip, L. S., & Chan, K. (2018). An exploratory study to conceptualize press engagement behavior with public relations practitioners. *Public relations review*, 44(4), 490-500.

- L'Etang, J., & Pieczka, M. (2006). Public relations education. *Public relations: Critical debates and contemporary practice*, 433-442.
- Levine, W. (2008). Communications and alumni relations: What is the correlation between an institution 's communications vehicles and alumni annual giving? *International Journal of Educational Advancement*. 8(3-4), 176–197
- Maity, B. (2022). Event promotion, advertising and public relations. *SAARJ Journal on Banking & Insurance Research (SJBIR)*. www.saarj.com
- Martin, K., & Quan-Haase, A. (2013). Are e-books replacing print books? Tradition, serendipity, and opportunity in the adoption and use of e-books for historical research and teaching. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 64(5), 1016–1028.
- McMillin, L. (2014). *Do Sports and Public Relations Make a Winning Combination for Schools? - How public relations is utilized in the Ole Miss Athletics Department and that of four other universities Honors Theses*. 573. https://egrove.olemiss.edu/hon_thesis/573
- Moody, J. (2023, June 7). The Current State of the NIL. *Inside Higher Education*. <https://www.insidehighered.com/news/students/athletics/2023/06/07/two-years-nil-fueling-chaos-college-athletics>
- Moore, A. J. (2011). Go for the goal: How pro sports teams score with social media. *Public Relations Tactics*, 18(3), 11.
- Mullin, B. J., Hardy, S., & Sutton, W. A. (2007). *Sport marketing* (3rd ed.). Champaign, IL: Human Kinetics

- Paek, H. J., Hove, T., Jung, Y., & Cole, R. T. (2013). Engagement across three social media platforms: An exploratory study of a cause-related PR campaign. *Public Relations Review*, 39(5), 526-533.
- Petersen, Jeffrey and Judge, Lawrence W. (2021) "Reframing the Collegiate Facilities Arms Race: The Looming Impact of NIL and Conference Realignment," *Journal of Applied Sport Management* 13(2).
- Petrovici, A., & Dobrescu, T. (2013). Public relations in sports. A case study. *Gymnasium*, 14(2), 121-127.
- Price, J. & Murnan J. (2004) Research limitations and the necessity of reporting them, *American Journal of Health Education*, 35(2), 66-67, DOI: 10.1080/19325037.2004.10603611
- Ruihley, B. J., Pratt, A. N., & Carpenter, T. (2016). The role of public relations in college athletics: Identifying roles, tasks, and importance of public relations. *Journal of Applied Sport Management*, 8(1), 11.
- Sen, S., & Bhattacharya, C. B. (2001). Does doing good always lead to doing better? Consumer reactions to corporate social responsibility. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 38(2), 225–243. <https://doi.org/10.1509/jmkr.38.2.225.18838>
- Serbanica, D. and Constantinescu, M. (2016). Using public relations in sports. *Romanian Journal of Marketing*, 11(2), 30-35
- Siau, K., & Han, L. (2020). COVID-19 pandemic management and control: Effects of information and communication technologies.
- Sriramesh, K. (2003). The dire need for multiculturalism in public relations education: An Asian perspective. *Journal of Communication Management*, 7(1), 54-70.
- Stoldt, C., Dittmore, S.W., & Branvold, S.E. (2006). Sport public relations. *Human Kinetics*.

- Tafesse, W. (2016). Conceptualization of brand experience in an event marketing context. *Journal of Promotion Management*, 22(1), 34-48.
- Taylor, A. (2022). NCAA V. ALSTON: The Future of College Sports In the Name, Image and Likeness Era. *Rutgers University Law Review* 75(1)
- Tenderich, B. (2019). Content Creation in Public Relations. In *Public Relations* (pp. 82-96). Routledge.
- Tenjido, D. (2021). Pay to Play Is Here-NCAA's Power Grip Loosens. *University of Denver Sports & Entertainment Law Journal*, 24, 29-56.
- Tomic, M. (2007). *Sportski Menadzment. Belgrade: DATA STATUS.*
- Tsegyu, S., Garba, S., & Muhammad, U. (2024). Utilizing Public Relations to Combat Misinformation and Promote Evidence-Based Policies for Sustainable Development.
- Valentini, C., & Kruckeberg, D. (2012). New media versus social media: A conceptualization of their meanings, uses, and implications for public relations. In *New media and public relations* (pp. 3-12). Peter Lang.
- Wade, M., & Shan, J. (2020). Covid-19 Has accelerated digital transformation, but may have made it harder not easier. *MIS Quarterly Executive*, 19(3).
- Wernick, A. (1991). Global promo: The cultural triumph of exchange. *Theory, Culture & Society*, 8(1), 89-109. <https://doi.org/10.1177/026327691008001005>
- Wodicka, R., Swartz, N. & Peaslee, L. (2012) Taking the classroom to town hall: Advancing public affairs education through university municipal collaborations. *Journal of Public Affairs Education*, 18(2), 271-294, DOI: 10.1080/15236803.2012.12001684

Yang, S., Fichman, P., Zhu, X., Sanfilippo, M., Li, S., & Fleischmann, K. R. (2020). The use of ICT during COVID-19. *Proceedings of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 57(1), e297.